

OBSERVED PERFORMANCE OF A RC WALL-FRAME BUILDING DURING THE FEBRUARY 2023 TURKIYE EARTHQUAKE AND PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT USING FRPS

Cem Tura, Bogazici University, Turkey, cem.tura@boun.edu.tr

Yusuf Sahinkaya, Istanbul Medeniyet University, Turkey, yusuf.sahinkaya@medeniyet.edu.tr

M. Fethi Güllü, Harran University, Turkey, fethigullu@harran.edu.tr

Ugur Demir, Izmir Institute of Technology, Turkey, ugurdemir@iyte.edu.tr

Kutay Orakcal, Bogazici University, Turkey, kutay.orakcal@boun.edu.tr

Alper Ilki, Istanbul Technical University, Turkey, ailki@itu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

In this study, results of nonlinear response history analysis are presented for an existing RC wall-frame building, which has suffered collapse-level damage during the devastating February 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquakes. Performance analysis results for two building configurations are compared; first for the existing building configuration generated upon on-site observations, and second, for a hypothetical configuration in which the structural walls and columns are retrofitted using externally-bonded FRP sheets. Analysis results reveal that in its existing configuration, mostly due to detailing deficiencies, a collapse-level performance was not unexpected; whereas FRP strengthening of the building would have resulted in collapse-prevention performance.

KEYWORDS

Building, collapse, damage, earthquake, FRP, performance, reinforced concrete, retrofit

INTRODUCTION

According to the damage assessment database of the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, the number of severely damaged or collapsed buildings affected by the Kahramanmaraş 2023 earthquake sequence has exceeded 250,000. The experience of the authors as a part of an official reconnaissance mission in the earthquake-affected region showed that the majority of these buildings could be rehabilitated prior to the earthquakes and thus, most of the casualties and economic loss could have been prevented. Even though limited in number compared to the RC moment frames, deficient RC shear wall buildings or wall-frame buildings have also been heavily damaged or collapsed. Beside the advantages of shear walls in limiting the seismic displacement demands on buildings due to their high lateral stiffness, inadequate amount or improper arrangement of the walls in the structural system, as well as inadequate amount or poor/non-ductile detailing of reinforcement may lead to fatal consequences, as the walls are subjected to significant force and ductility demands during large earthquakes. The response of such deficient shear walls is generally characterized by non-ductile failures as a result of poor confinement provided by the boundary element reinforcement, and/or brittle shear failure caused by insufficient shear strength (Layssi et al., 2012). A large number of these vulnerable walls in the existing building stock necessitates rehabilitation actions to prevent brittle flexural or shear failure. Notwithstanding that conventional techniques on strengthening of shear walls are effective in improving seismic behavior of a building, they may add significant weight to the structure and consequently alter the seismic demand. As an alternative to the conventional strengthening techniques, the use FRP confinement has been found to be quite effective for the strengthening of existing deficient shear walls. Paterson and Mitchell (2003) investigated the use of adding an RC collar and FRP confinement on strengthening of existing shear walls with inadequate lap splices at the critical plastic hinging regions. Khalil and Ghobarah (2005) reported the effectiveness of FRP confinement in

boundary columns combined with FRP or steel anchors, in improving the ductility and shear strength of the walls. Mosallam and Nasr (2017) studied the impact of FRP laminates on enhancing the seismic response of the shear walls. On the other hand, Mostofinejad and Anai (2012) concluded in their experimental study that applying externally bonded FRP wraps on only the boundary elements of the wall could be sufficient to provide sufficient ductility.

In the present study, based on the observations from one of the visited project sites in Antakya, typical damage and possible reasons behind the severe damage/complete collapse of four identical shear wall/frame building blocks, experienced during the recent Kahramanmaras earthquakes, are scrutinized. A nonlinear model of the structural system of a typical block is generated and nonlinear response history analyses are conducted in order to estimate response characteristics of the existing structure, first, considering the reinforcement and detailing characteristics (and deficiencies) of structural members observed on-site, and secondly, for a hypothetical configuration in which the shear wall boundary regions and column plastic hinge regions are strengthened (confined) using FRP materials. The analysis results show that strengthening of the wall boundary regions and the column plastic hinge regions using FRP wrapping significantly enhances the seismic performance of the structure, and may be a promising intervention towards complying with the collapse prevention (CP) performance level for existing buildings incorporating ductility/confinement deficiencies.

PROPERTIES OF THE BUILDING AND GROUND MOTION CHARACTERISTICS

Within the scope of the study, four identical 13-story RC wall/frame buildings in the Antakya/Hatay region, which are located at the same construction site, are investigated. The state of the building blocks recorded after the earthquakes is illustrated in Figure 1. As shown in the figure, (i) Block 1 has completely collapsed, (ii) Block 2 was on the verge of collapse, with severe damage to the structural members and 5% residual drift ratio measured along the ground story, (iii) the ground story of Block 3 has completely collapsed, and (iv) Block 4 was under construction and was completed up to 9th story, and experienced moderate to severe structural damage during the earthquake.

Figure 1: State of the buildings after the earthquake

From Block 4, which was still under construction during the earthquake, detailed measurements of the structural system/element dimensions were taken and the structural system drawings were generated. Reinforcement characteristics of the structural members were also collected, through observations on visible reinforcement located in the incomplete top floor of one of the blocks, as well as observations on the damaged structural members that experienced spalling of cover concrete. The structural design

drawings of the project were also attained at a later time, and on-site observations were validated via comparison with the design drawings. The project includes four identical blocks which consist of 13 stories with varying story heights between 2.65m and 2.90m, with a total building height of 35m. From design drawings, it was determined that the local soil class at the site is ZD ($(V_s)_{30}$: 180-360 m/s), the concrete class is C30 (30MPa characteristic compressive strength), reinforcing steel grade is B420C (420 MPa characteristic yield strength). The structural system of buildings is combination of moment resisting frames with rectangular structural walls that are mostly perpendicular to the perimeter axes of the building, together with two U-shaped core walls located at the center, as shown in Figure 2a. From the plans, it was observed that one of the deficiencies in the structural system configuration is discontinuous frames in the X direction of the building, together with perimeter beams in the X direction that do not frame into vertical members, both of which may prevent development of an effective frame action and lead to insufficient lateral stiffness in this direction.

Figure 2: Typical structural plan of the buildings

Although the member cross-sectional dimensions and longitudinal reinforcement amounts used in the construction of the building were mostly in compliance with the design drawings, several deficiencies in detailing were noticed, including; improper detailing of the stirrups in the beams, columns, and wall boundary regions (90-degree hooks instead of 135-degree), absence of crossies both in columns and walls, and insufficient anchorage detailing of horizontal web reinforcement in the walls (where the horizontal web reinforcement bars are not properly anchored to the confined wall boundary regions). Damage observations on the structural members in the buildings showed: (i) crushing of core concrete, (ii) buckling and post-buckling rupture (due to low-cycle fatigue) of longitudinal reinforcement, (iii) post-buckling rupture of column starter bars (despite adequate anchorage length), (iv) significant residual drift (approximately 5% drift ratio along the ground story of Block 2), most of which were associated with concrete crushing due to deficient detailing for ductility. Typical types of damage observed on the structural elements are demonstrated in Figure 3, and typical confinement details in design drawings are compared with construction applications in Figure 4.

a) concrete crushing at the base of a shear wall (insufficient anchorage of horizontal web reinforcement can also be observed)

b) core crushing in a column and buckling of column reinforcement

c) post-buckling rupture of column starter bars in a collapsed block

d) post-buckling rupture of beam reinforcement

Figure 3: Observed typical damages

a) Columns

b) Structural walls

Figure 4: Design vs. constructed confinement details (absence of crossies in construction can be observed)

Although the epicenter of the M_w 7.7 Pazarcik earthquake was located in Kahramanmaras, the highest PGAs were recorded in the Hatay region. In the current study, a representative ground motion record is selected for the response history analysis of the building, obtained from one of the closest stations (Station#3123) to the construction site, which also had comparable soil conditions with the site. The station is located at a distance of 1.3km to the site (Figure. 5). The $(V_s)_{30}$ value for the station is reported to be 470m/s, and the peak ground acceleration recorded at the station during the M_w 7.7 Pazarcik earthquake is 0.66g.

Figure 5: Epicenter of the sequential earthquakes and locations of the building site and the station

When the generated 5% damping response spectra for the considered ground motion record is compared with the current Turkish Building Seismic Code (TBSC, 2018) DD1 level (2% probability of exceedance in 50 years) design spectrum (for which a code-compliant building is expected to implicitly satisfy collapse-prevention performance), it is observed that spectral accelerations of the record are below the code spectrum at short periods (Figure 6). On the other hand, spectral accelerations around the vicinity of the fundamental period range of the buildings (1.4s~1.8s) significantly exceed the design spectrum values. As shown in Figure 6, the N-S component of the ground motions recorded at Station#3123 has significantly higher spectral acceleration values in this fundamental period range, compared with the E-W component. It must be noted that both the collapse direction of Block 1 and the excessive residual drift that developed in Block 2 were observed to be in the N-S direction, which is compatible with this particular characteristic of the ground motion record (see Figure 1).

Figure 6: Comparison of response spectra with the TBSC2018 DD1 level design spectrum (ZD soil class)

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS MODEL

Based on the structural design drawings and on-site observations, a nonlinear analysis model for the existing (as-built) configuration of the building is first generated using CSI Perform3D in order to assess whether the observed collapse-level performance can be simulated under the measured ground motion record (Figure 2b). Then, a second model is generated where the column plastic hinge regions along the first two stories of the building and the structural wall boundary regions also along the first two stories of the building are strengthened using FRP wrapping. In generation of the model, existing material strengths are defined as 39MPa compressive strength for C30 class concrete and 504MPa yield strength for B420C grade reinforcement, in compliance with TBSC2018. Frame elements are modeled using the lumped plasticity approach (plastic hinges) and structural walls are modeled using fiber model elements. Hysteretic backbone parameters for the plastic hinges, as well as effective stiffness multipliers for the frame elements are defined in compliance with ASCE41-17, considering insufficient (non-compliant) confinement characteristics due to the aforementioned detailing deficiencies (widespread 90-degree hooks on beam stirrups and column ties, lack of crossties on columns) in the columns and the beams. In the second model, modeling (backbone) parameters of the beams are not modified, but columns are assumed to have rigid-indefinitely plastic moment vs. plastic rotation behavior (without any strength loss) after FRP application (Figure 7). In both models, flexibility or nonlinear behaviour of the

beam-column joints is not explicitly included in the model. Instead, rigid end offsets at columns ends and elastic end offsets at beam ends are defined in compliance with ASCE41-17. The beams are modelled using rectangular cross-sections and the rigid diaphragm assumption is adopted for the floor slabs. To define the hysteretic behavior of the plastic hinges, peak-oriented hysteresis rules are adopted for the beam plastic hinges, while perfectly plastic hysteretic behaviour (with no hysteretic stiffness degradation) is used for column hinges (Figure 8).

In modeling of structural walls, due to the absence of cross-ties and use of 90-degree hooks on the ties at the wall boundary regions, unconfined concrete models are used to define concrete stress-strain relationships used in the fiber model elements for walls in the as-built building model configuration. In the FRP-strengthened model configuration, concrete stress strain relationships generated for FRP-confined wall boundary regions (as described in the next section) are used to represent the compressive stress-strain behavior of wall boundary region concrete fibers (Figure 7). An effective shear modulus of $0.5G$ is used to define the linear elastic shear behavior of the wall model elements, and 5% viscous damping is assumed in all analyses. The vertical component of the ground motion is not explicitly considered in the analyses. Instead, the dead weight of the structure is amplified by a margin of $0.2S_{DS}$ (which corresponds to 42% increase in dead load), as prescribed by TBEC2018. Preliminary analysis results obtained for this building showed that considering the vertical component of ground motion as an increase (as opposed to decrease) in dead weight is the more critical case, in terms of the displacement and deformation demands developing on the structure.

a) stress strain relationships used for concrete in fiber model elements at wall boundary regions

b) sample backbone curves for column plastic hinges

Figure 7: Stress strain relationships and backbone curves

Figure 8: Hysteretic behavior of the plastic hinges

FRP STRENGTHENING

ACI Committe 440 (ACI 2017) is considered for the confinement of the reinforced concrete columns and wall boundary regions within the scope of the study, together with other documents cited below.

According to ACI 440.2R-17 (ACI 2017), compressive strength of FRP wrapped concrete (f_{cc}) and the corresponding axial compressive strain of concrete (ε_{cc}) can be estimated using Eqs. (1-8).

$$f_{cc} = f_c + \psi_f 3.3 \kappa_a f_l \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{cc} = \varepsilon_c \left[1.50 + 12 \kappa_b \left(\frac{f_l}{f_c} \right) \left(\frac{\varepsilon_f}{\varepsilon_c} \right)^{0.45} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\kappa_a = \frac{A_e}{A_c} \left(\frac{b}{h} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\kappa_b = \frac{A_e}{A_c} \left(\frac{h}{b} \right)^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

$$f_l = \frac{2E_f n t_f \varepsilon_f}{D} \quad (5)$$

$$D = \sqrt{h^2 + b^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{f_l}{f_c} \geq 0.08 \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon_f = 0.004 \leq \kappa_\varepsilon \varepsilon_{fu} \quad (8)$$

where, κ_a and κ_b are the section shape factors; A_e and A_c are the cross-sectional area of effectively confined and gross sections; ε_f and f_l are the effective FRP strain ($0.004 \leq \kappa_\varepsilon \varepsilon_{fu}$) and the maximum confining pressure due to FRP jacket, respectively; ψ_f is the strength reduction factor for FRP (0.95 for fully wrapped setion); ε_{fu} is the design rupture strain of FRP provided by the manufacturer; and κ_ε is the efficiency factor for FRP strain (recommended as 0.55). The properties of the Carbon FRP (CFRP) material used in the study are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Features of the CFRP sheets considered during hypothetical seismic strengthening

Feature	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	Ultimate strain (%)	Thickness (mm)
Value	4200	240	2	0.166

According to ACI Committee 440 (ACI 2017), it is not advisable to use FRP jacketing for structural members with cross-sectional aspect ratios (h/b) greater than 1.5 or face dimensions (b or h) exceeding 900 mm unless testing proves the effectiveness of FRP in confining rectangular sections (for strength enhancement). Based on the results of the experimental studies conducted by Ghatte et al., (2018) and Akgun et al., (2010), where the effectiveness of FRP wrapping in reinforced concrete columns with cross-sectional aspect ratios of 2 and 3 have been demonstrated under reversed cyclic lateral loads and axial loads, respectively (particularly in terms of displacement capacity), the columns of the examined building are considered to be suitable for external FRP jacketing towards improvement of the displacement capacity, since the h/b ratios were only slightly over 3 for the columns with the maximum cross-sectional aspect ratios. In order to meet the plastic rotation demand obtained from the analyses, column plastic hinge regions along the first two stories of the building are wrapped with four layers of CFRP sheets. The sectional analysis of a typical sample column (axially loaded up to 27% of $f'_c b h$) with the highest plastic rotation demand is then performed to determine its plastic rotation capacity before and after strengthening. The concrete stress-strain curves and moment-rotation relationships for this column before and after CFRP jacketing are presented in Figure 9.

For the reinforced concrete shear walls, in order to satisfy the compressive strain demands at the boundary regions of the walls along the first two stories of the building, free boundaries of the U-shaped core walls are wrapped with five layers of CFRP sheets, while the end zones of rectangular walls are wrapped with three layers. For the walls, the wrapping is performed on three sides and CFRP cross-ties/anchors are used at the inner end of the boundary regions to enhance the effectiveness of the confinement (Figure 10). In the study conducted by El-Sokkary et al. (2013); the ultimate capacity of the FRP anchors was designed to be 35% of the ultimate strength of the straight fiber composite to account for the strength reduction caused by the bent fibers. Furthermore, the experimental study carried out by Orton et al. (2008), showed that such anchors should be at least double amount of the longitudinal FRPs to safeguard the anchors and have the failure in longitudinal FRPs. Therefore, the total cross-

sectional area of CFRP cross-ties/anchors in this study has been considered as the twice amount of horizontal CFRP sheets used for external wrapping. The stress-strain relationships of unconfined, three-layer and five-layer CFRP confined concrete, as well as the strengthening details, are shown in Figure 10. It should be noted that the corners of the sections to be externally jacketed with FRP sheets should be rounded to a radius of (r_c) 30 mm before FRP confinement.

Figure 9: Stress-strain and moment-rotation relationships for a representative column before and after FRP wrapping

Figure 10: Details on CFRP-confinement of U-shaped walls

ANALYSIS RESULTS

The influence of the aforementioned CFRP strengthening on the seismic response and performance of a typical block is evaluated via comparison of nonlinear response history analysis results obtained for the existing as-built configuration and the hypothetical FRP-strengthened configuration of the structural system. In order to evaluate the performance of the building, maximum story drift profiles along the height of the structure, compressive strain demands at structural wall boundary regions, and plastic rotation demands at column ends are investigated. Shear force demands developing along the height of the structural walls are also scrutinized.

Analysis results for the story drift profile for the as-built configuration of the building show that excessive story drifts are expected on the building under the selected ground motion record, as shown

in Figure 11a. Maximum story drift ratios along the height of the structure in Y direction (along the North-South component of the strong ground motion) reach up to 6.4%, with a residual (permanent) drift of 6% at the end of the analysis. Considering that Block 1 has collapsed and Block 3 has experienced a severe residual drift of 5% along the ground story (near collapse), both in the Y direction, analysis results obtained for the as-built configuration of the building are in agreement with site observations. On the other hand, when structural wall boundary regions and column plastic hinge regions are confined using FRP wraps, analysis results obtained for the FRP-strengthened configuration of the model show that the maximum story drift ratio reduces to 4.6%, with a residual drift ratio of 3.4%. Reduction in the drift demands obtained for the FRP-strengthened building configuration is found to be associated with preventing of crushing of concrete in the FRP-confined wall boundary regions, and to a lesser extent, elimination of strength loss (reduction of moment capacity) in the backbone curves used to model the behavior of the column plastic hinges. It must be mentioned that the drift demands on the FRP-strengthened building configuration are still large; however, this is not unexpected considering that the spectral acceleration values of the ground motion record significantly exceed the DD1 level (2% probability of exceedance in 50 years) design spectrum in the vicinity of the fundamental period range of the building (see Figure 6). The large drift demands obtained for the FRP-strengthened building are also associated with the strength loss behavior adopted in the ASCE 41 backbone curves used in definition of the beam plastic hinges. When strength loss in the beam plastic hinges are not considered, the maximum drift demand on the FRP-strengthened building reduces from 4.6% down to 3%. Figure 11(a) also shows that the drift demands in the positive Y direction are almost identical for the as-built and FRP-strengthened model configurations. This is because plastic deformations develop mostly under displacements in the negative Y direction of the building, which was also observed during the on-site damage observations.

a) story drift profiles for the as-built and FRP-strengthened models b) strain demands and collapse prevention strain limits for the U-shaped walls c) strain demands and collapse prevention strain limits for the rectangular walls

Figure 11: Comparison of the as-built and FRP-strengthened model configurations

When the structural wall boundary region compressive strains shown in Figure 11b and 11c are examined, it is observed that the strain demands are localized along the ground story of the building, which is expected, and analysis results estimate compressive strains up to 0.058 at free boundaries of the U-shaped core walls, and 0.018 at the boundaries of the rectangular walls. Unconfined concrete at boundary regions of the walls are obviously expected to crush under such large strain demands (Figure 10a), which is believed to be the primary reason why these buildings suffered collapse or collapse-level

damage. However, after FRP strengthening, compressive strains at the wall boundary regions reduce down to 0.0092 and 0.0032 at U-shaped core wall boundaries and the rectangular wall boundaries, respectively. When these compressive strain demands obtained from the analysis are compared with the strain capacities corresponding to FRP-strengthened wall boundary regions in this building (Figures 11b and 11c), it is observed that the strain demands fall below the FRP-confined strain capacities, since the FRP confinement was designed to meet these strain demands, and the FRP-strengthening methodology considered in this investigation will prevent crushing of concrete at the wall boundary regions and will likely bring the structure up to collapse prevention performance level.

When plastic rotation demands developing on the columns (Figure 12a) are investigated, analysis results show that plastic column hinges form only along the first two stories of the building. For the as-built configuration of the building, plastic rotation demands on some of the columns (0.027 rad maximum) exceed the collapse prevention plastic rotation limits defined in ASCE41-17 for these columns. This is in general agreement with core crushing observed on some of the ground floor columns during the on-site damage inspection. For the FRP-strengthened building configuration, similarly to wall compressive strain demands, column plastic rotation demands also decrease (maximum demand reduces down to 0.0092 rad), primarily due to reduction in the drift demands on the building. In this case, the plastic rotation demands do not exceed the plastic rotation capacity of the FRP-strengthened columns (Figure 12a), since, similarly to the walls, the FRP confinement was designed to meet these rotation demands. Furthermore, irrespective of analysis results, FRP-wrapping of the plastic hinge regions of columns with deficient confinement detailing (90-degree hooks and no crossties) would be a rational approach.

Figure 12: Comparison of column plastic rotation and building shear force demands

Finally, as a representative comparison, shear force demands obtained from the two model configurations (as-built and FRP-strengthened) are compared with the shear capacity of one wall segment (U-shaped core wall leg in Y direction) that is subjected to relatively high shear force demands. The analysis results depicted in Figure 12b show that the shear force demands do not differ significantly for the as-built and FRP-strengthened model configurations. This is expected since in both model configurations, the walls experience flexural yielding and FRP-strengthening does not notably increase

the flexural strength of the walls. However, in both cases, shear force demands are very close to the shear capacity of the wall segment, especially up to the mid-height of the building. Considering the aforementioned anchorage deficiencies in the horizontal web reinforcement of the walls (the horizontal web bars are anchored as straight bars in the cover concrete of the wall boundary regions), the wall shear capacity in the as-built state of the building can be significantly lower, making the walls susceptible to shear failure. Therefore, FRP-strengthening of the walls (with externally-bonded FRP sheets or horizontal strips applied along its web) can be considered as an additional FRP-retrofit scheme. However, another consideration might be that FRP-wrapping of the wall boundary regions (to improve flexural ductility) would also serve to improve the anchorage characteristics of the horizontal web bars within the wall boundary regions, possibly eliminating the anchorage deficiency especially along the height where cover crushing in the wall boundary regions are expected (along the first two story heights of the walls; see Figure 11). However, FRP-strengthening of walls against anchorage deficiencies in wall shear reinforcement is a subject that needs to be investigated in much more detail.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, seismic performance analyses were conducted on an existing RC wall-frame building that has suffered collapse-level damage during the February 2023 Kahramanmaraş-Pazarcık earthquake, under a real ground motion time history that was recorded at a station with very close proximity of the building. Nonlinear response history analysis results obtained using a model configuration that reflects the as-built characteristics (and deficiencies) of the building were compared with the on-site damage observations. A second hypothetical model configuration, in which the structural walls and columns in the building are retrofitted using externally-bonded FRP sheets, was also generated, and the expected influence of FRP-strengthening on the seismic response and performance of the building was investigated. Based on the analysis results, the following conclusions are deduced:

- During the earthquake, the building was subjected to seismic demands that significantly exceeded the spectral ordinates of the code spectrum.
- Analysis results obtained using the as-built model configuration of the building were in agreement with the observed damage and performance of the building.
- Ductile detailing deficiencies, including lack of crossties and presence of 90-degree tie hooks in the wall boundary regions and column plastic hinge regions, significantly impaired the seismic performance of the building, leading to very large displacement (drift) demands associated with crushing of concrete particularly in the wall boundary regions. Resulting large deformation (strain or plastic rotation) demands were shown to exceed collapse-prevention deformation limits for the walls and columns, in their as-built state with insufficient confinement characteristics.
- The FRP-retrofit scheme proposed in this study for the wall boundary regions and column plastic hinge regions was shown to be a very promising intervention to bring the expected seismic performance of the building to the level of collapse prevention, not only reducing the displacement demands on the structure and the deformation demands on the walls and columns to a more reasonable level, but also increasing the deformation capacities of the walls and columns sufficiently to meet the deformation demands.

CITATIONS

Akgun, D., Demir, C., Ilki, A., “Axial behavior of FRP jacketed extended rectangular members constructed with low strength concrete,” 5th International Conference on FRP Composites in Civil Engineering, Beijing, September, 2010.

American Concrete Institute Committee 440 (2017). Guide for the design and construction of externally bonded FRP systems for strengthening concrete structures, ACI 440.2R-17, Farmington Hills, Miami.

American Society of Civil Engineers (2017). Seismic evaluation and retrofit of existing buildings, ASCE/SEI 41-17, Reston, Virginia.

- El-Sokkary, H., Galal, K., Ghorbanirenani, I., Leger, P., Tremblay, R. 2013. “Shake table tests on FRP-rehabilitated RC shear walls”, *ASCE, Journal of Composites for Construction*, Vol. 17, No. 1, 79-90.
- Ghatte, H. F., Comert, M., Demir, C., Akbaba, M., and Ilki, A. 2019. “Seismic retrofit of full-scale substandard extended rectangular rc columns through CFRP jacketing: test results and design recommendations, *ASCE, Journal of Composites for Construction*, Vol. 23, No. 1.
- Khalil, A., & Ghobarah, A. (2005). Behaviour of rehabilitated structural walls. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, 9(3), 371–391.
- Layssi, H., Cook, W. D., & Mitchell, D. (2012). Seismic response and CFRP retrofit of poorly detailed shear walls. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 16(3), 332-339.
- Mander, J.B., Priestley, M. J. and Park, R. (1988), “Theoretical stress-strain model for confined concrete”, *J.Struct. Eng.*, 114(8), 1804-1826.
- Mosallam, A. S., & Nasr, A. (2017). Structural performance of RC shear walls with post-construction openings strengthened with FRP composite laminates. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 115, 488-504.
- Mostofinejad, D., & Anaei, M. M. (2012). Effect of confining of boundary elements of slender RC shear wall by FRP composites and stirrups. *Engineering Structures*, 41, 1-13.
- Orton, S., Jirsa, J., Bayrak, O. 2008. “Design considerations of carbon fiber anchors.”, *ASCE, Journal of Composites for Construction*, Vol. 12, No. 6, 608-616.
- Paterson, J., & Mitchell, D. (2003). Seismic retrofit of shear walls with headed bars and carbon fiber wrap. *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 129(5), 606–614.
- Perform3D V.7.0.0. (2018). Nonlinear Analysis and Performance Assessment for 3D Structures, Computers and Structures Inc.
- Turkish Building Seismic Code (2018). Official Gazetta 30364, Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD), Ankara, Türkiye.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The support of Istanbul Technical University, Boğaziçi University and Harran University as well as the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change are gratefully acknowledged. We also acknowledge the assistance of Civil Engineer Ali Hoca for providing us the blueprints of the case study buildings.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data will be made available upon reasonable request after the authors complete publication of journal papers.